

THE BIOPLASTIC BUBBLE WRAP - MADE UP OF CELLULOSE

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Abstract: *In this fast growing World the plastics have managed to made its huge impact on human life by being a major source of our daily needs. Due to which it has also given rise to environmental hazards by being an issue of biodegradability. The number of steps has already been taken to control the use of plastics but to purge the use of the non-biodegradable plastics our main focus is on making it environment friendly. Some plastics such as bubble wrap which are basically used to provide protection to delicate and fragile objects are filled with polyethylene and needs an industrial composting and takes hundreds of years to degrade as a result it occupies a considerable amount of space within the landfills making it challenging for the environment to deal. So the basic idea is to make a compostable and biodegradable bubble wrap from cellulose extracted from barks of trees (cellulose being an abundant polymer of nature). The cellulose plastic or bioplastic's byproduct can also be used as fuels and feedstock in production of other chemicals because of mechanical properties of cellulose this cellulose bubble wrap can be flexible, bio-renewable, decomposable, temperature resistance, chemically versatile and will coordinate with the nature's loop because of the properties that cellulose holds. It is quite an innovative and cost-effective approach for making a bioplastic bubble wrap which can easily be decomposed along with the green wastes into the soil. The wrap will exactly mimic the plastic bubble wrap in terms of providing protection, lightweight and cost-effective. It will be designed in such a way that in today's fast moving world the industries can produce a definite amount of wraps and will also provide benefits to the customers and retailers.*

Keywords: bubble wrap, cellulose, compostable, biodegradable